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PERSONAL VALUES AND EXPECTATION – AN EMPIRICAL STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO SAIL, SALEM

MALA JAYASHREE J*

**Assistant professor in Commerce,
Sri Krishnaswamy College for Women,
Anna Nagar, Chennai, Tamil Nadu.*

Abstract

Personal values of an individual provide an internal reference about what is good and beneficial; important and useful; beautiful and desirable; productive and constructive. Values are shown in the form of behaviour. This research paper investigates the Values offered by Organization and the Personal Values of the employees SAIL, Salem, one of the Maharashtra awardees of the public sector undertakings for its best industrial practices. For this purpose the respondents are selected by using proportionate random sampling method. The responses are processed and analyzed through Henry Garrett Ranking Technique. It is found that the personal values viz., Flexible, precise, adaptable and team-oriented are found to be the top ranked whereas opportunities for professional growth, high pay for good performance, enthusiastic about the job performance and job security are top ranked among the company offers.

INTRODUCTION

When a child is born, the child does not possess any values or expectation. As a child grows up, the values are learned from the parents and adults who spend time in rising up. The personal values are not only learned from teachings of adults also through the learning by watching and observing. Personal values help to solve common human problems for survival. Personal values lay the foundations of law, custom and tradition.

Values are also connected with moral and ethical systems and are seen as a useful way of examining interpretations of what is perceived as 'right' and 'wrong', ethical inclination and intention to act. Values are also a key element of an organization's culture and its ethics. At the organizational level there is general agreement that organizational culture involves a set of cognitions that are shared by members; that these cognitions are acquired through social learning and socialization processes. Values also account for considerable stress and conflict when they clash with the values of other people or the

organization's values. Surveys indicate that many employees experience conflict between their own and their company's values¹.

Organizational values constitute culture of the organization – the set of beliefs that people share about what sort of behaviour is correct or incorrect. The organization aligns with the personal values, the individual feel liberated, and able to concentrate well in their work. Thereby the individuals not only brings energy, creativity, enthusiasm in work, also brings commitment to the well being and success of the organization. When these organizational beliefs conflict with the individual personal values, people are likely to distance themselves psychologically from the organization. There is a fundamental rift between employee and employer. There is a failure to share the same beliefs and ways of doing things. If employees do perceive a conflict of values, they casually accommodate this but fail to be committed to the goals and aspirations of the organization in the long term. They will see the role they play in the company as a means to an end and at this stage their commitment ceases.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Values relate to our very purpose in life and they serve as guiding principles. If workplace values and personal values are in not alignment, it makes the employees dissatisfied, unhappy, and will definitely do not generate the results. It's a compelling fact that organizations which does not have core values will find it increasingly difficult to attract as well as to retain talent workforce. Aligning the work place values with personal values is difficult. In the workplace, values are ubiquitous. Values are the basis of organizational culture. Values of organization indicate what is most important for employees and the values are always transferred by the senior employees to the new comers. It is important to find common values that contribute to the success of both employees and the organization.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Michael James (1997)² researched on titled “A conceptual framework for aligning managerial behaviors with cultural work values”. This paper has demonstrated how specific managerial behaviors are affected by various cultural dimensions. The matching of managerial behavior with cultural work values has enormous applications in the selection and training process of American managers overseas. Better preparation for overseas assignments can be enhanced. Managers whose behavioral style is consistent with the host's cultural work values are more likely to adapt better to the overseas assignment and function more effectively. Any gaps that exist between the manager's behaviors and the host's cultural work values can be reduced through the use of training programs. Training programs can emphasize which behaviors are most consistent with the host's cultural work values. Culture shock can be minimized and the likelihood of a successful overseas assignment increased. The premature return of expatriates, and the astronomical costs associated with it, can be minimized. It is concluded that the use of western management practices without the necessary adaption to local cultural values and conditions is likely to lead to rejection by host nationals. Adopting to cross – cultural differences will have a bearing on the economic performance of American corporations.

Jackson Paul & Harris Lisa (2003)³, have researched on “E-business and organizational change: Reconciling traditional values with business transformation”. This research paper addresses the problems faced by such companies involved demonstrate new business models and offer customer novel propositions. It argues that over and above the technological matters, major organizational change issues must be recognized and addressed for e-business solutions to be realized successfully. It also suggest, because of the need to redesign business processes and structures, change organizational culture, and

¹ Peter Navarro, (2005), “What the Best MBAs Know- How to Apply Greatest Ideas Taught in the Best Business Schools, Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi, pp.232.

² Michael James (1997) “A Conceptual framework for aligning managerial behavior with Cultural Work Values”, *International Journal of Commerce & Management* 1997. Vol.7 No. 3 /4 , Pg. 81 -101 ; ISSN : 1056-9219.

³ Jackson, Paul; Harris, Lisa (2003), “E-business and organizational change: Reconciling traditional values with business transformation”, *Journal of Organizational Change Management, Volume.16.Issue. 5,(2003):pp.497-511.*

engage in education and training. This research has adapted case study method. The case studies have illustrated some of the challenges faced by incumbent firms in terms of e-business transformation, while also highlighting some surprising advantages over the supposedly more agile industry newcomers. The research concludes as to skilled change agents and leaders capable of championing e-business will be needed. Resistance at all company levels may need to be overcome, with a corresponding need to build commitment and consensus around e-business strategies. At the same time, care needs to be taken not to "throw the baby out with the bath water" and recognize that significant aspects of the "old" business structure or process may well have enduring value in the e-business context. Only by recognizing and rising to these challenges and dilemmas, and devoting sufficient time, resources and expertise to them, will companies make a success of their e-business ventures.

*Abbas J. Ali & Ali Al-Kazemi (2005)*⁴, researched on "The Kuwaiti Manger: Work Values and Orientations". This research investigated work values and the loyalty (Commitment to hard work, profession, and principles) of 762 managers in Kuwait. 6 public organization and 10 private sector organization were chosen for the study randomly. First the study investigated whether or not work values and loyalty differ across selected demographic and organizational variables. Secondly the study attempts to tackle a common stereotype which projects managers in Kuwait as individuals who adhere to traditional rather than the modern work values. Lastly the study examines the relationships between work values and loyalty scales. The results indicated that managers scored high on work value and loyalty. Furthermore, there was a high positive correlation between the two measures. Demographic and organizational variables had significant influence on managerial orientations. Specifically, expatriates and female managers showed a high commitment to work values and loyalty.

*Jeremy Reynolds (2005)*⁵ has done a research on "In the Face of Conflict: Work-Life Conflict and Desired Work Hour Adjustments". This study helps to integrate the work-life and work hour's literatures by examining competing predictions about the relationship between work-life conflict and the desire for paid work. Using data from the 1997 National Study of the changing Workforce (N=2,178), the author find that work-life conflict makes women want to decrease the number of hours they work whether the conflict originates at home or at work. The analysis of this research also has some implications for public policy. Further this analysis also indicates that recent organizational and governmental actions may not satisfy the demand for fewer hours of work. Men only want to decrease their hours when work-life conflict originates at work, and some men facing frequent conflict actually want to increase their hours. The author also find that having children does not increase the likelihood of wanting to work fewer hours but having a higher income does.

*Ruth Alas & Christopher J. Rees (2006)*⁶, researched on "Work-related Attitudes, Values and Radical Change in Post-Socialist Contexts: A Comparative Study". This research draws attention to the transfer of management theories and practices from traditional capitalist countries such as the USA and UK to post-socialist countries that are currently experienced radical change as they seek to introduce market reforms. It is highlighted that the efficacy of this transfer of management theories and practices is, in part, dependent upon the extent to which work-related attitudes and values vary between traditional capitalist and former socialist contexts. The research highlights that practices such as Human Resource Management (HRM) and Organization Development (OD) are inextricably associated with conceptions surrounding culture and society, as well as to variables such as job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The main aim of this research is to compare various attitudes and values of employees in traditional capitalist countries and post-socialist countries. On the findings of an attitudinal survey of (N=5914) workers in 15 countries. The research concludes that certain aspects of the attitudes and values of workers in post socialist countries and traditional capitalist countries differ significantly.

⁴ *Abbas J Ali & Ali Al-Kazemi (2005), "The Kuwaiti Manger: Work Values and Orientations", Journal of Business Ethics (2005) 60: 63-73. Print ISSN 0167-4544, Online ISSN 1573-0697*

⁵ *Jeremy Reynolds (2005). "In the Face of Conflict: Work-Life Conflict and Desired Work Hour Adjustments", Journal of Marriage and Family, Vol. 67, No. 5 (Dec., 2005), pp. 1313-1331.*

⁶ *Ruth Alas & Christopher J Rees (2006) 'Work-related Attitudes, Values and Radical Change in Post-Socialist Contexts: A Comparative Study', Journal of Business Ethics (2006), 68: 181-189.*

Specifically, these differences were found in respect of context-related and job-related attitudes, and also in relation to the importance that the respondents attached to the subject of ethics more generally. The implications of the study are discussed particularly in relation to the transfer of management theory and practice between traditional capitalist and post-socialist contexts.

*Deanna de Zilwa (2007)*⁷ has attempted a research on “Organizational Culture and Values and the adaptation of academic units in Australian universities”. This research explores connections between the organizational culture and values of academic units in Australian universities and their efforts to adapt to external environmental pressures. It integrates empirical findings from case studies with theories of organizational culture and values and adaptations. It identifies seven dimensions of academic unit’s organizational culture and values that influenced how case study academic units adapted, then patterns of heterogeneity and homogeneity within these dimensions are noted and their associations with different modes of adaptation are discussed in this research. This research identifies challenges that relate to academic unit’s organizational culture and values-their heterogeneity and fluidity, escalating tensions between some units and university managers, for others tendencies towards inertia and resistance towards change. This research opine that if academic units in Australian Universities are to survive in external environments that situate them ‘far from equilibrium’ they need to constantly monitor changes in their external environments and modify their modes of adaptation to suit their current environmental challenges.

*Susan Durbin et al., (2008)*⁸, have researched on “Professional insights Diversities in an Organization Context”. The purpose of this study is to report on a research day on the theme of diversity held at the Centre for Employment Studies Research – formerly the Employment Studies Research Unit at the University of the West of England, Bristol, Uk. This report brings together a number of important themes, highlighting and synthesizing the complex relationship between anti-discrimination legislation and the role of organizations and employees.

*Jennifer Tomlinson & Jean Gardiner (2009)*⁹, have researched on ”Organizational approaches to flexible working perspectives of equality and diversity managers in the UK”. The purpose of this research is to first explore flexible working (FW) as an important but under researched dimension of equality and diversity (E&D) and, second, contribute to employment relations debates by exploring organizational perspectives on flexible working and how these connect with business strategies and the regulatory context. In depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with 12 E&D managers in 10 public and private sector organizations. Four organizational rationales for FWAs were identified from the data. These were FWA constructed as: an individual employee benefit: a means of improving operational effectiveness: an integral part of organizational strategy: and as a means of addressing structural social inequalities. This research paper outlines different rationales for flexible working and shows how some organization are able to develop flexible policies that are more equitable and effective than other organizations.

*Laurel A. McNall et al., (2010)*¹⁰, have researched on “Flexible work arrangements, job Satisfaction, and Turnover Intentions: The Mediating Role of Work –to-family Enrichment”. The authors examined the relation between the availability of 2 popular types of flexible work arrangements (i.e., flextime and compressed work week) and work-t-family enrichment and, in turn, the relaxation between work-to family enrichment and (a) job satisfaction and (b) turnover intentions. In a sample of 220 employed working adults, hierarchical regression analyses showed that work-to family enrichment mediated the relation between flexible work arrangements and both job satisfaction and turnover intentions, even after

⁷ *Deanna de Zilwa (2007). “Organizational Culture and Values and the adaptation of academic units in Australian universities”, Higher Education, Vol.54, No.4 (oct., 2007), pp.557-574.*

⁸ *Susan Durbin, Lin Lovell and Janet Winters (2008), “Professional insights Diversities in an Organization Context”, Equal Opportunities International, Volume.27, No.4, 2008, pp.396-400.*

⁹ *Jennifer Tomlinson and Jean Gardiner (2009), “Organizational approaches to flexible working perspectives of equality and diversity managers in the UK”, Equal Opportunities Internationals, Volume.28. No.8 2009, pp.671-686.*

¹⁰ *Laurel A. McNall, Aline D. Masuda, and Jessica M. Nicklin (2010), “Flexible work arrangements, job Satisfaction, and Turnover Intentions: The Mediating Role of Work –to-family Enrichment”, The Journal of Psychology, 2010, 144(1), 61-81.*

controlling for gender, age, marital status, education, number of children, and hours worked. Thus, the availability of flexible work arrangements such as flextime and compressed work week seems to help employees experience greater enrichment from work to home, which in turn, is associated with higher job satisfaction and lower turnover intentions. The authors discuss the implications for research and practice. This study suggests from the practical perspective organizations consider offering specific work policies such as flextime and compressed workweek schedules to facilitate work-to-family enrichment. Employees expect an increasing level of flexibility from employers so they can better meet the demands of their work and personal lives.

*Marieken Ven Den Tooren & Jan De Jonge (2010)*¹¹, have researched on “The role of matching job resources in different demanding situations at work: A Vignette Study”. This research examines human service employees’ beliefs about the availability, relevance and use of specific types of job resources (i.e., cognitive, emotional and physical) in similar types of demanding situations at work. To gain a better understanding of these intra-psychic processes assumed to underline the relation between job demands, job resources, and job-related outcomes, a quasi-experimental survey study with vignettes was developed. Results showed that different patterns could be observed between the availability, relevance use of matching and non-matching job resources in a physically demanding situation at work. No such differences were observed in a cognitively and emotionally demanding job. Further, it was shown that there generally seems to be a dominant role for emotional job resources in the job stress process. Whereas the role of physical job resources and, to a lesser extent, cognitive job resources appears much weaker and mainly restricted to corresponding types of job demands. Finally, results suggested that employees who are faced with a particular type of job demands may take advantage of both matching and non-matching job resources, implying that the ‘matching hypothesis’ is a probabilistic rather than a static principle.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To examine the Values offered by Organization and the Personal Values of the employees.

METHODOLOGY

The study is made using both primary and secondary data. Secondary data is collected from various sources like books, journals and internet. The unit chosen for the study is The Steel Authority of India Limited (Salem). For the purpose of the study the respondents are selected by following proportionate random sampling method. The researcher worked to contact 40% of the total employees which may be sufficient to reflect the views of the organization. The employees are interviewed through questionnaire exclusively prepared for this purpose.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study will generate interest among the academicians and practitioners who are interested in the subject matter. This study may also open up new frontiers of knowledge. On this object the study enables management practitioners to gain an insight and design ways of improving the effectiveness of their organization by bridging between the employee expectations in terms of values.

STATISTICAL TOOL USED

In view of complexity of data, the responses are processed and analyzed by using Henry Garrett Ranking Technique. This technique was used to rank the values and offers in the organization, SAIL. In this method the respondents were asked to rank the given values and offers according to the magnitude of their opinion. The order of merit given by the respondents was converted into ranks by using the following formula.

¹¹ *Marieken Ven Den Tooren & Jan De Jonge (2010), “The role of matching job resources in different demanding situations at work: A Vignette Study”, Journal of Occupational and Organizational psychology (2010), 83, 39-54.*

$$\text{Percentage Position} = \frac{100(R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where, Rij - Ranking Position; Nj - Total No. of Ranks

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The following table shows the characteristics of the employees in terms of their values are discussed. For this purpose, the researcher has taken the characteristics into twelve heads viz., flexible, adaptable, precise, team-oriented, ready to share information, easygoing, supportive, decisive, result-oriented, interested in making friends at work, enthusiastic about the work and willing to experiment. The characteristics are scored by using Henry Garrett Ranking Technique and discussed in the following table.

Table No. 1 - Individuals Characteristics in terms of values

S.No.	Values	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
1	Flexible	35118	65.2	I
2	Adaptable	33762	62.6	III
3	Precise	34684	64.3	II
4	Team-oriented	32108	59.6	IV
5	Ready to share information	30207	56.0	V
6	Easygoing	27537	51.1	VI
7	Supportive	26668	49.5	VII
8	Decisive	26093	48.4	VIII
9	Result-oriented	24565	45.6	IX
10	Interested in making friends at work	17728	32.9	XI
11	Enthusiastic about the work	18987	35.2	X
12	Willing to experiment	15983	29.7	XII

(Source- Primary data)

The above table No.1 describes the total score, mean score and rank of personal characteristics of employees in terms of values. From the above analysis it is found that the maximum of the employees are having 'Flexible' character is ranked first followed by the other personal characteristics 'Precise', 'Adaptable', 'Team-oriented' and 'Ready to share information' are occupied the second, third, fourth and fifth rank. The sixth, seventh, eighth, ninth and tenth position occupies the characteristics 'Easygoing', 'Supportive', 'Decisive', 'Result-oriented' and 'Enthusiastic about the work'. On the other hand, the characteristics 'Interested in making friends at work' and 'willing to experiment' are ranked eleventh and twelveth. It is found from the analysis that maximum of the employees are having the characteristics 'Flexible' and 'Precise' at the maximum level while the characteristics such as 'Interested in making friends at work' and 'Willing to experiment' at the minimum level.

Organizational values are the standards to which reference is made for judging acceptable standards for the organization as it interacts with its external environment and the norms of behavior for

individuals with the organization. Values are inherent in a firm’s mission and goals; its strategies and structure; allocation of resources; codes of practice, policies and procedures; and its actions¹². Values and beliefs are part of the cognitive substructure of an organizational culture. Values are intimately connected with moral and ethical codes, and determine what people think ought to be done¹³. Organizational values and beliefs constitute the foundation of an organization’s culture. They also play a key role in influencing ethical behaviour¹⁴.

The table No.2 illustrates the opinion of the company offering in terms of value. *Henry Garrett Ranking Technique* is used to rank, the total score, mean score and rank are given in the following table. The employees rank the opportunities for professional growth as first, followed by high pay for good performance, enthusiastic about the job performance, job security, praise for good performance as second, third, fourth and fifth rank.

Table No. 2 - Opinion of employees towards company offers

S.No.	Values	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
1	Enthusiastic about the job performance	33749	62.6	III
2	Opportunities for professional growth	34277	63.6	I
3	High pay for good performance	33849	62.8	II
4	Job Security	33082	61.4	IV
5	Praise for good performance	29075	53.9	V
6	A clear guiding philosophy	28339	52.6	VI
7	A low level of conflict	26886	49.9	VII
8	An emphasis on quality	26036	48.3	VIII
9	A Good reputation	25387	47.1	IX
10	Respect for the individual’s rights	17987	33.4	XI
11	A sense of social responsibility	19184	35.6	X
12	Long hours	16113	29.9	XII

(Source- Primary data)

It is inferred from the above table that a clear guiding philosophy, a low level of conflict, an emphasis on quality, a good reputation and a sense of social responsibility are ranked as sixth, seventh, eighth, ninth and tenth rank. While respect for the individual’s rights and long working hours are ranked as eleventh and twelfth rank. The above table indicates that the opportunities for professional growth is awarded maximum score is awarded while respect for the individual’s rights and long working hours are awarded minimum scores.

CONCLUSION

¹² Ann Lawrence & Peter Lawrence (2009), pp.299.

¹³ Andrew D. Brown, (1995), -Organizational Culture, pitman publishing, London, 1995, pp.21

¹⁴ Robert Kreitner , Angelo Kinicki, Marc Buelens- Organizational Behaviour Instructors’ Edition- Mc Graw Hill Publishing Company Edition (2002), pp.67.

Values relate to what an individual wants and in what order he/she wants them. Personal values exist in relation to cultural values, either in agreement with or divergence from prevailing norms. Different cultures reflect values differently and to different levels of emphasis. It is found that the personal values viz., Flexible, precise, adaptable and team-oriented are found to be the top ranked whereas opportunities for professional growth, high pay for good performance, enthusiastic about the job performance and job security are top ranked among the company offers.

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